
The FDI and Economic Growth in the Western Balkans: The Role of Institutions

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the impact of the foreign direct investment (FDI) and institutional quality on economic growth of the Western Balkan economies – Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Montenegro, North Macedonia and Serbia. The conventional wisdom says that FDI plays a significant role in economic development and that institutional development may affect this relationship as well. Using a panel data analysis for a period of 20 years (2000-2019) and in contrast to this conventional wisdom, the study shows that FDI has a significantly negative impact on growth within the sample countries. At the same time, the results indicate that institutional development has significantly negative or no role on growth directly. The results depend on the proxy used for institutional development. Furthermore, when FDI and institutional development measures are interacted, both indicators including their interaction terms become primarily insignificant. This may be due to the fact that the institutions within the sample countries are at low levels of development to make any significant impact on either growth or FDI-growth relationship.

Keywords: *institutional development, foreign direct investment, FDI, economic growth, transition economies, Western Balkan.*

1. Introduction

Impacts of foreign direct investment (FDI) and institutional development attracted a significant attention among researchers. Depending on underlying conditions in which particular state is, these variables may cast different effects on economic growth. However, the overall effect of FDI and institutional development is expected to be positive. In particular, it is expected that FDI would lead to spillovers and technological innovation of know-how to the less developed economies (Kisswani et al., 2015). For this reason, any type of FDI is generally welcomed, especially in the case of transition economies such as those from the Western Balkans. Significance of FDI is closely related to the development of financial sectors and institutions, political stability, and the quality of human capital. Perhaps among the main reasons for low levels of the FDI inflow into Balkan region are the underdevelopment of financial sectors and institutions.

As economic growth is affected by a number of factors, the same is true for FDI inflows. According to Hunady and Orviska (2014), a country's economic openness, labour and firing costs, income level and public debt as well as financial and economic crisis have significant impact on FDI. At the

same time, the study finds no significant effect of corporate tax rates on FDI. All these point to the importance of institutional quality and effectiveness for effective impact of FDI on growth.

The Western Balkans countries in particular and transition economies in general are in dire need for FDI inflows that would support infrastructural and other developmental projects that could boost economic growth. The main objective of this study is to look at the effect of FDI and institutional development on economic growth focusing on the Western Balkan countries – Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Kosovo, Montenegro, North Macedonia and Serbia.

For this research we are going to apply the pooled OLS and fixed-effects methods developed by Driscoll-Kraay (1998). This method is the best suitable for the sample where time period (T) is larger than group (N). By using Driscoll-Kraay standard errors regression we will be able to meet the objective.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. *Section 2* provides a literature review. *Section 3* describes the data and methodology used. *Section 4* is reserved for discussion of empirical results. Finally, *Section 5* provides concluding remarks.

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2. Literature Review

The relationship between economic growth and the level of FDI on one side and institutional quality/development on the other has attracted considerable attention among scholars, yet results are far from being conclusive. In the following subsections, we are discussing briefly these studies and their findings.

2.1. FDI–Economic Growth

Over the years, the developed world attracted majority of the international FDI. However, in recent years this trend is changing. According to the World Investment Report (UNCTAD, 2019), the global flows of FDI in 2018 decreased to \$1.3 trillion (from a \$1.5 trillion in 2017) with a fall of 13 percent, being the lowest since the 2008 global financial crisis. The inflows to developing countries have been steadily rising with an annual 2 percent increase and have now reached a share of 54 percent of the global FDI amount, an all-time high.

When it comes to the empirical studies, the literature provides conflicting results. For instance, Blomstoerm et al. (1992) found a positive correlation between FDI inflows (measured as percentage of GDP) and GDP per capita across developed countries. They argue the countries with higher per-capita income level benefit from FDI inflows more than countries in the lower per capita income level. According to them, local businesses in poor countries are too far behind in technological and human capital levels, making them less competitive and less attractive to large corporations. Similar findings are reported by Bengoa & Sanchez-Robles (2003), Zhang (2001), Elboiashi (2015) and Borenstein (1998) who emphasized how FDI inflows are highly significant for economy only in case the host country meets minimum requirements of human capital needed, i.e., that the economy is absorptive enough to use and efficiently utilize the FDI.

Kiswani et al. (2015) analyzed the influence of FDI on real GDP rates in Estonia, a country that within a short period of time moved from planned- to market-based economic system, adopting institutional changes and joined the EU and EMU. Using the cointegration tests, the authors found a long-term relationship between the FDI and the real GDP without a significant deviation between the two in the long-run. Similarly, in the case of ten European transitional economies, Asteriou et al. (2005) used two proxies for FDI, a ratio of FDI net inflows to GDP and the ratio of the net portfolio investments to GDP. They found that the first proxy exhibits a significantly positive impact, while the second proxy is found to have a negative but insignificant impact on economic growth.

In contrast to the above studies, there are also authors who challenge the positive impact of FDI on economic

growth. For instance, FDI inflows may lead to transfer of technology and know-how, efficient resource allocation, and contribute to skills transfer among domestic workforce. However, it may also reduce the labor productivity and local firms' comparative advantages as the results show that firms not receiving FDI had better performance in certain regional industries (Lutz & Talavera, 2004; Minić et al., 2021). Further, contrary to findings reported by Asteriou et al. (2005) above, Anetor (2020) found that FDI has significantly negative impact, while portfolio investment has a positive but insignificant impact on economic growth of sub-Saharan African countries.

Finally, Carkovic and Levine (2002) used generalized method of moments (GMM) panel estimator on 72 countries between 1960 and 1995. The results show no significant impact of FDI on growth either in developed or developing economies. Similarly, no significant relationships whatsoever between the two was reported by Lyroudi et al. (2004) as well. They focused on 17 transition economies (Central and Eastern Europe region) using Bayesian analysis.

A number of studies are also focusing on the EU and the Western Balkan countries. Using panel data analysis and covering the 1989-2008 period, Angelopoulou and Liargovas (2014) studied the FDI-economic growth relationship among three different country groups (27 EU, 16 EMU member states and 18 transition economies) with an emphasis on different levels of economic integration within the unions as well as across the states individually. In short, the study suggests there is no robust causality between FDI and economic growth in the three country groups – findings in line with Lyroudi et al. (2004). Likewise, during the 2002-2012 study period, FDI inflows had insignificant impact on value added, employment, and exports of manufacturing sectors of the Western Balkan countries (Estrin & Uvalic, 2016).

2.2. Institutional Quality and Economic Growth

In similar fashion, the literature on institutional development and economic growth relationship attracted a lot of attention among researchers. Most commonly used measures of institutional development in the literature are property rights, freedom of press, bureaucratic procedures, democracy levels, political stability, business environment indices and others. While research results are mostly straightforward, suggesting the positive impact of highly-developed institutional framework on economic growth, there is a wide variety of factors that influence the institutional development itself. Consequently, Murtaza and Faridi (2016) found that efficient government and functional democracy lead to institutional efficiency that eventually lead to economic growth in the case of Pakistan. In the case

of sub-Saharan African countries, institutional quality contributes to economic growth both directly and indirectly through public debt (Sani et al., 2019). Similarly, reviewing the literature over the 1992–2016 period, Urbano et al. (2019) claim that institutions contribute to economic growth through entrepreneurship.

Controlling for bureaucratic quality, property rights and political stability of nations are found to be crucial for economic growth and investment (Knack & Keefer, 1995), while corruption exhibits a negative impact on economic growth, as measured by per capita income (Easterly, 1999; Minović et al., 2021). Similarly, Scully (1988) argue that societies with a lower degree of political, civil and economic freedom are less than twice as efficient and productive as societies with higher degrees of freedoms. In other words, societies that are more politically open, adhering to the rule of law and relying on market-influenced allocation of resources were developing at a three times faster rate and were more than double as efficient as the states where these freedoms were limited.

In a similar manner, studies claim that in case when the political authority in a society is owned and exercised only by a restricted number of individuals (an elite segment with great political power as is the case with majority of the Western Balkan countries), the same group will shape institutions and regulations to benefit only a small proportion of the society (Nigar, 2015). Hence, this leads to non-efficient resource allocation, directing them to the upper-income level of society, and hindering the economic growth prospects (Sonin, 2003). This ability of the politically powerful individuals taking advantage of weak institutions and directing resources in accordance with their personal benefit, is explained through a lack of democracy reflected in political and wealth inequality (Sonin, 2003; Nigar, 2015).

2.3. FDI, Institutional Quality and Economic Growth

According to recent studies, both FDI and institutional quality bring about economic growth. Thus, improving overall institutional quality would lead to better economic growth and FDI inflows (Van Bon, 2019; Hayat, 2019; Raza et al., 2019) These results, however, are more evident for the low and middle-income countries. As for the high-income countries, the study found that FDI inflows, in fact, slow down economic growth (Hayat, 2019). Furthermore, Haini (2020) found positive and significant impact of the rule of law on economic growth and it plays complementary role to financial development. The complementary role of institutional quality is also found by Kutan et al. (2017) who detect positive impact of FDI inflows on growth as well. In contrast, according to Jude and Levieuge (2015), FDI will affect economic growth in developing countries only once a certain level of institutional quality is reached. Hence, before attracting FDI, developing countries should enhance their institutional quality.

In contrast, Agbloyor et al. (2016) found no impact of either FDI or institutions on growth in sub-Saharan African

countries (SSA). Furthermore, the results show that the impact of FDI on growth is not affected by institutions as well. However, institutions do affect economic growth directly and indirectly via FDI once countries with developed financial markets are excluded. Also focusing on SSA, Asamoah et al. (2019) found positive and negative effects of institutional quality and FDI on economic growth. On top of that, while positive on growth, institutional quality hinders the positive effects of FDI and trade openness on growth (Nguyen et al., 2018). That institutions affect the impact of FDI on growth and that it needs to reach a threshold to make it positive is confirmed in the SSA, MENA, Europe, Asia and America regions (Trojette, 2016).

Hence, this study contributes to the existing literature on FDI-institutions-growth relationships in a number of ways. First, the existing literature on FDI-growth, institutions-growth, FDI-institutions-growth relationships provides mixed results. Second, these relationships have not been properly addressed to the Western Balkan countries. These countries are on the EU membership waiting list and it is dependent, to a great extent, on countries' institutional development that is not at the desired level. Third, the sample countries belong to the transition economies group of countries that are undergoing structural changes moving from command economy to market economy systems. As such, they belong to developing economies and the existing literature indicate that the impact of FDI and institutions on growth within those countries are different from their impacts on growth of developed, well-established market economies.

3. Data and Methodology

3.1. Models and method used

Numerous estimation techniques have been used in the literature, from the pooled OLS (POLS), the random effect (RE), the fixed effects (FE), to the instrumental variable (IV) estimator and the generalized methods of moments (GMM) method. The GMM method is suitable for models with a long (N) and a short (T). However, our sample consists of a short (N) and a relatively long (T) as we have a panel consisting of only 5 countries and covering the 20-year period. Hence, we cannot use the GMM technique.

The RE method assumes that each country in our sample has its own error term and for this method to work these individual error terms are not to be correlated with our explanatory variables. If this assumption is not true, the RE estimation results would be inconsistent and biased. In contrast, the FE method, also known as the least squares dummy variable (LSDV), assumes different constants for each country in the sample (Asteriou et al., 2005; Flannery & Hankins, 2013).

However, many panel data suffer from cross-sectional or 'spatial' dependence as claimed by Driscoll and Kraay (1998). This is especially true for macroeconomic studies with non-random selection of groups (states, countries, or industries) over time where these groups are 'subject to both

observable and unobservable common disturbances’. Failing to tackle the issue of spatial dependence, standard techniques would produce consistent parameters, but with inconsistent standard errors (Driscoll & Kraay, 1998; Hoechle, 2007). In other words, for standard errors in panel data studies to be valid, cross-sectional individuals should be uncorrelated (Vogelsang, 2012). Transforming the orthogonality conditions addresses issues of spatial and temporal dependence. Even though the spatial correlation consistent standard error estimator requires large T, it is found to provide superior results even in finite-samples with short T when compared to standard techniques that do not cater for spatial dependence (Driscoll & Kraay, 1998).

For this purpose, we use the STATA command ‘*xtscc*’ developed by Hoechle (2007). It provides POLS and FE (within) estimates with Driscoll and Kraay (1998) standard errors. The Hausman test (Hausman, 1978) is used to choose between POLS and FE models. However, to get robust Hausman test in case of spatial and temporal dependence, we follow Hoechle (2007) who fit the auxiliary regression suggested by Wooldridge (2002) with Driscoll and Kraay standard errors. The null hypothesis of no FE, i.e., that $E(\alpha + \varepsilon_{it}|X_{it}) = 0$, is tested. A significant p -value ($p < 0.05$) of the F stat from the test of $\gamma = 0$ rejects the null and provides support for FE. Otherwise, we should rely on POLS estimator (see Hoechle, 2007).

Thus, in line with Azam and Ahmed (2015), we use the following model to estimate the impact of FDI and institutional development on economic growth:

$$Y_{it} = \alpha + \beta FDI_{it} + \delta ID_{it} + \theta X_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (1)$$

where for country i (the cross-sectional dimension) at time t (the time dimension), Y_{it} is the annual real per capita GDP growth rate, FDI_{it} represents FDI inflows, ID_{it} is a measure of institutional development, X_{it} is a vector of all control variables, and ε_{it} is a random error term that captures all other variables. Similar model has been used by (Hayat, 2019; Trojette, 2016; Van Bon, 2019). Estimation using model (1) above will show what the effects of the FDI and institutional development are on economic growth in our sample countries.

Furthermore, to see whether the FDI-growth relationship depends on institutional development, we introduce an interaction term to equation (1) as presented in equation (2) below:

$$GDP_{it} = \alpha + \beta FDI_{it} + \delta ID_{it} + \vartheta (FDI_{it} \times ID_{it}) + \theta X_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (2)$$

where, $FDI_{it} \times ID_{it}$ represents the interaction variable. Other terms are as defined earlier.

Having an interaction term in our dynamic panel data model will help us evaluate the impact of lagged value of growth, FDI, institutional development and our control variables on growth. At the same time, it will help us evaluate the impact of institutional development on FDI-growth nexus. Finally, in line with Hayat (2019), we transform all variables in natural logarithm form except GDP, FDI, and institutional quality variables.

3.2. Data

In order to investigate the relationship between FDI and institutional development on one side and economic growth on the other, the study utilizes few panel data techniques on the Western Balkan countries – Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Montenegro, North Macedonia and Serbia.* These economies are relatively small, developing and going through a transition from planned/command to market economy.

In this regard, the study will use annual time series data of the selected macroeconomic indicators. All data are sourced from the World Bank’s database and cover the period of 2000-2019, making it a total of 20 years.† As we are covering 20-year period and 5 countries (cross-sectional units), there should be 100 observations in total (20 x 5). However, as a number of countries reported no data the total number of observations for each variable may not be the same. However, we are dealing with a strongly balanced panel.

Following the existing literature, this study uses the real per capita GDP growth (GDP) as a measure for economic growth. Several studies use different FDI proxies. Still, the most common proxy for FDI is net FDI inflows as percentage of GDP. Institutional development is measured either by overall institutional quality (control of corruption, political stability, and rule of law) from the Heritage Foundation (Procházka & Čermáková, 2015) or by institutional development variable provided by the World Governance Indicators (WGI) developed by Kaufmann et al. (2010). Kaufmann et al. (2010) mentions six indicators of institutional quality, namely: estimates of control of corruption (CCE), government effectiveness (GEE), political stability (PSE), regulatory quality (RQE), rule of law (RLE), and voice and accountability (VAE). These indicators are measured on the scale from -2.5 to +2.5 where the highest scale implies superior institutional quality and vice versa.

Following Buchanan et al. (2012), we consider all those indicators individually to test their impact on growth and

* Although Croatia belongs to the Western Balkans, we excluded it from the sample as she joined the EU on 1 July 2013. On the other hand, there are sufficient data for Kosovo and thus we excluded Kosovo from the study as well.

† We opt for this period due to the fact that majority of the Western Balkan countries went through turbulent times during the ‘90s and it took some years for these countries to get their economies back on track.

FDI-growth relationship. We cannot use them jointly in a singly equation as these indicators are highly correlated (Globerman & Shapiro, 2002; Buchanan et al., 2012). For this reason and in line with Knack and Keefer (1995), Globerman and Shapiro (2002), Buchanan et al. (2012) and Sani et al. (2019), we use the principal component analysis (PCA) to construct the institutional quality (IQ) index based on those indicators.

As for control variables, we use a number of macroeconomic variables to control their impacts on economic growth as the literature point out to their significance in determining economic growth. In particular, we use gross capital formation (GCF) representing investment (Ibrahim et al., 2017), trade openness (TO), labor force (LF) as measured by total number of labor force, and inflation (I) (Beck et al., 2014; Bist, 2018; Ibrahim et al., 2017; Sabir et al., 2019; Swamy & Dharani, 2019; Trojette, 2016).

Table 1 – Descriptive statistics.

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
GDP per capita growth	100	3.7	2.703	-5.997	9.311
FDI - net inflows	88	7.047	5.595	.536	37.272
Institutional development	99	58.069	7.45	36.6	71.3
Institutional quality index	100	-.687	.212	-1.382	-.303
Control of corruption	100	-.404	.236	-1.177	.023
Government effectiveness	100	-.152	.575	-.96	2.766
Political stability	100	-.247	.428	-1.643	.816
Regulatory quality	100	-.018	.325	-.856	.885
Rule of law	100	-.349	.294	-1.272	.335
Voice and accountability	100	.032	.187	-.638	.336
Gross capital formation	100	24.388	6.15	9.165	41.177
Trade openness	100	90.523	19.101	22.492	138.827
Labor force - total	100	1,406,622.2	993,922.84	231,387	3,354,615
Inflation - GDP deflator	100	6.281	12.533	-2.758	86.826

Error! Reference source not found. presents the descriptive statistics of the variables used in this study. A significant variation of the real GDP per capita growth is evident in the Table with mean and standard deviation being 3.7 percent and 2.7 percent respectively. The lowest, negative, GDP per capita growth of – 5.99 percent is recorded in Montenegro and the highest of 9.31 percent in Albania. The same is true for FDI and institutional development as measured by the Heritage Foundation. The FDI is ranging from 0.54 percent in North Macedonia to 37.27 percent of GDP in Montenegro. Institutional development is lowest in Bosnia and Herzegovina and highest in North Macedonia. A great deal of variation is detected in the case of inflation that ranges from a minimum of -2.76 percent to a maximum of 86.83 percent. To take logarithm, we add a constant number 3 to the inflation rate. As described earlier, all institutional quality variables are in the -2.5 and 2.5 range.

4. Analysis of Results

Table 1 provides the estimated results based on of *Eq (1)* using the pooled ordinary least square (OLS) and the fixed-

effects (FE) estimators with Driscoll-Kraay standard errors and various indicators for institutional development. In particular, models (1) and (2) are using institutional development (ID) proxy based on the Heritage Foundation data; models (3) and (4) rely on the institutional quality (IQ) index constructed applying PSA on six institutional quality indicators developed by Kaufmann et al. (2010). Furthermore, each of these six indicators are used individually. Hence, control of corruption (CCE), government effectiveness (GEE), political stability (PSE), regulatory quality (RQE), rule of law (RLE), and voice and accountability (VAE) and used in models (5) and (6), (7) and (8), (9) and (10), (11) and (12), (13) and (14), and (15) and (16), respectively.

As pointed out in the previous section, we use the Hausman test as suggested by Hoechle (2007) to determine whether we should rely of FE or OLS results. Based on this test, FE estimation results are preferred expect when ID is used in model (1) where we should rely on results provided by OLS estimator. Furthermore, the R^2 results from Table 1 reveal that our models explain from 71.4 percent to 78.5 percent variation in economic growth.

In general, our results indicate that FDI has significantly negative impact on economic growth in the selected Western Balkan countries. These results are in line with results reported by Anetor (2020) and partially with those of Lutz and Talavera (2004). As for institutional development, the results are inconclusive and even conflicting depending on a proxy used. ID, a proxy from the Heritage Foundation, reveals significantly negative impact of institutional development on economic growth. Having in mind the overall (under)development of institutions in our sample countries this result comes as no surprise and support arguments provided by Nigar (2015) and Sonin (2003). In other models, our proxies for institutional development are either positive or negative but insignificant in all relevant models.‡

‡ Significantly negative impact is found in the case of regulatory quality estimate (RQE) using OLS in model (11). However, based on the Hausman test, we should

rely here on FE estimation results from model (12).

Table 1 - FDI-Institutions-Growth nexus: GDP per capita as dependent variable

VARIABLES	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)	(12)	(13)
	POLS	FE	POLS	FE	POLS	FE	POLS	FE	POLS	FE	POLS	FE	POLS
FDI	-0.085** (0.030)	-0.138** (0.048)	-0.059 (0.034)	-0.143** (0.051)	-0.059 (0.034)	-0.143** (0.051)	-0.045 (0.043)	-0.141** (0.043)	-0.143 (0.071)	-0.141* (0.057)	-0.095* (0.040)	-0.143** (0.049)	-0.066 (0.036)
ID	-0.177** (0.045)	-0.039 (0.049)											
IQ			1.322 (1.203)	2.566 (2.034)									
CCE					1.188 (1.081)	2.306 (1.828)							
GEE							-1.043 (0.714)	3.318 (1.579)					
PSE									1.826 (1.015)	0.243 (0.748)			
RQE											-4.444** (1.445)	-3.089 (1.816)	
RLE													-0.250 (2.425)
VAE													
GCF	5.475** (1.558)	3.719** (0.823)	3.737* (1.642)	3.902** (1.023)	3.737* (1.642)	3.902** (1.023)	3.580* (1.519)	4.504*** (0.975)	2.940* (1.132)	3.548** (1.097)	5.484** (1.557)	3.485** (0.971)	3.367 (1.191)
TO	-1.436 (0.692)	1.769 (1.440)	-0.889 (0.986)	1.170 (0.794)	-0.889 (0.986)	1.170 (0.794)	0.048 (1.195)	0.672 (1.360)	-0.372 (0.911)	1.765 (1.640)	0.250 (0.925)	2.866* (1.263)	-0.011 (2.075)
LF	-0.016 (0.282)	2.587 (5.252)	0.384 (0.392)	-1.910 (8.363)	0.384 (0.392)	-1.910 (8.363)	0.301 (0.351)	-0.228 (4.821)	0.311 (0.364)	3.364 (5.337)	0.101 (0.221)	6.117 (6.279)	0.297 (0.341)
INF	-0.428* (0.169)	-0.394* (0.174)	-0.396 (0.190)	-0.321 (0.174)	-0.396 (0.190)	-0.321 (0.174)	-0.280 (0.214)	-0.339 (0.199)	-0.196 (0.242)	-0.364 (0.175)	-0.368* (0.140)	-0.387* (0.180)	-0.350 (0.205)
Constant	4.744 (8.077)	-48.978 (70.975)	-	16.578 (115.810)	-	15.747 (115.227)	-	-6.967 (64.665)	-	-62.811 (70.486)	-	-104.432 (86.251)	-
Year Dummy	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Obs.	88	88	88	88	88	88	88	88	88	88	88	88	88
No. of groups	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
R ²	0.771	0.778	0.716	0.778	0.716	0.783	0.720	0.785	0.739	0.778	0.772	0.784	0.714
F-stat.	138.350	3930.461	121.206	5411.237	121.206	2569.580	143.064	7480.445	91.247	1629.249	17.603	7489.395	263.6
F-stat. p-val.	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)
Hausman	-	1.872	-	14.277	-	14.004	-	6.275	-	27.484	-	10.490	-
Hausman p-val.	-	(0.282)	-	(0.012)	-	(0.012)	-	(0.050)	-	(0.003)	-	(0.020)	-

Note: Regression with Driscoll-Kraay standard errors. GDP - GDP per capita growth (annual %); FDI - Foreign direct investment, net inflows (% of GDP); ID - Institutional quality estimate; CCE - Control of corruption: estimate; GEE - Government effectiveness: estimate; PSE - Political stability: estimate; RQE - Regulatory quality: estimate; RLE - Rule of law: estimate; GCF - Log of Gross capital formation (% of GDP); TO - Log of Trade (% of GDP); LF - Log of Labor force - total; Log of Inflation - GDP deflator (annual %). Statistical significance level *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.10.

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Obs.	88	88	88	88	88	88	88	88	88	88	88	88	88
No. of groups	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
R^2	0.777	0.778	0.721	0.783	0.721	0.783	0.736	0.785	0.747	0.788	0.782	0.786	0.714
F -stat.	61.283	5399.392	94.365	3273.533	94.365	3273.529	120.158	2048.126	852.773	4119.241	200.439	401.769	444.18
F -stat. p -val.	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Hausman	-	1.762	-	23.027	-	23.430	-	4.973	-	27.719	-	13.839	-
Hausman p -val.	-	(0.302)	-	(0.005)	-	(0.005)	-	(0.073)	-	(0.003)	-	(0.012)	-

Note: Regression with Driscoll-Kraay standard errors. GDP - GDP per capita growth (annual %); FDI - Foreign direct investment, net inflows (% of GDP); ID - Institutional development index; IQ - Institutional quality; FDIxIQ - FDI & IQ interaction term; CCE - Control of corruption: estimate; FDIxCCE - FDI & CCE interaction term; GEE - Government effectiveness: estimate; FDIxGEE - FDI & GEE interaction term; PSE - Political stability: estimate; FDIxPSE - FDI & PSE interaction term; RQE - Regulatory quality: estimate; FDIxRQE - FDI & RQE interaction term; RLE - Rule of law: estimate; FDIxRLE - FDI & RLE interaction term; VAE - Voice and accountability: estimate; FDIxVAE - FDI & VAE interaction term; GCF - Log of Gross capital formation (% of GDP); TO - Total factor productivity: estimate; FDIxTO - FDI & TO interaction term; Labor force - total; Log of Inflation - GDP deflator (annual %). Standard errors in parentheses. Significance level *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.10$.

As for control variables, GCF is found to have significantly positive impact on growth in all models which is not the case with other variables (Anetor, 2020). In models (1) and (12), INF has negative and significant impact (Anetor, 2020), while significantly positive impact of TO is found only in model (12) (Nigar, 2015). Finally, LF has insignificant impact on growth with both positive and negative signs (Nigar, 2015).

In short, based on the estimation results from Table 1, we can conclude that when it comes to the Western Balkan countries, FDI decreases economic growth significantly. Based on the majority results, however, we find no direct impact of institutional development proxies on growth. This could be attributed to very low levels of institutional development within the sample countries as it is pointed in previous studies that they need to reach certain levels in order to affect growth after all (see Jude & Leveuge, 2015).

Now, we turn to

Table 2 that provides results for E_q (2) that investigates not only the impact of FDI and institutions on growth, but also whether the FDI-growth relationship depends on levels of institutional development. Based on the Hausman tests, the results based on FE estimations are to be preferred except in models (1) and (7) where we should rely on POLS.

In general, introducing interaction terms in our models makes majority of our main variables insignificant. For instance, FDI has significantly negative impact, in line with our previous results, only in models (12) and (14). In other models, we find it both positive and negative but insignificant. Similarly, majority of institutional development coefficients are insignificant. Significantly negative impact of institution on growth is confirmed only in model (1). However, the results indicate no significant impact of institution on FDI-growth relationship as interaction terms are statistically insignificant. Similar results are reported by Agbloyor et al. (2016), Asamoah et al. (2019), and Trojette (2016). It seems that both FDI and institutions need to be developed further to significantly affect economic growth. As pointed by Trojette (2016), the institutional development should reach a threshold to affect either growth or FDI-growth relationship.

5. Conclusion

In this study we revisited the FDI-growth and institution-growth relationships focusing on five Western Balkan economies. – Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Montenegro, North Macedonia and Serbia. Moving from the command to market economies, these countries underwent significant economic, political and social changes that led to structural and institutional changes as well.

Focusing on the 2000-2019 period and utilizing the Driscoll-Kraay standard errors regression, this study shows that FDI inflows has significantly negative impact on growth. The impact of institutional development, on the other hand, is inconclusive. While the overall institutional development proxy developed by the Heritage Foundation reveals the same impact on growth as FDI, the other proxies are predominantly insignificant. Furthermore, the interaction model indicates that the impact of FDI is insignificant although negative, while the results for institutional development remain the same. Nevertheless, all interaction terms are insignificant showing that neither FDI nor institutional development have impact on their individual impact on economic growth.

Hence, the overall (under)development of institutions in our sample countries is not sufficient to make significant impact on growth and FDI-growth relationship. Policymakers, thus, should focus on improving the overall quality of institutions and determine why FDI is not bringing about progress that it should.

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